

Job Hiring

April 28, 2026

1 Description

TechForYou, a leading technology firm, is hiring a software engineer based on candidates' likelihood of success, favoring those with higher potential.

1) **TechForYou relies on employees to assess an applicant's quality.**

- a) Imagine you are an applicant of TechForYou. How acceptable do you find it when an employee assesses the quality?
 - i) completely unacceptable
 - ii) somewhat unacceptable
 - iii) neutral
 - iv) somewhat acceptable
 - v) completely acceptable
- b) Please describe a situation where using employees would be beneficial for assessing the quality.
- c) Please describe a situation where using employees would be harmful for assessing the quality

RecruitTalent, a recruitment firm, collects resumes (including their technical skills, academic qualifications, experience, and portfolios) from applicants with criminal backgrounds.

RecruitTalent uses the collected data to develop an Artificial Intelligence (AI) to predict whether an applicant will succeed at the job.

2) **Instead of employees, the TechForYou now relies on RecruitTalent's AI to assess an applicant's quality.**

- a) Imagine you are an applicant of TechForYou. How acceptable do you find it when an AI assesses the quality?
 - i) completely unacceptable
 - ii) somewhat unacceptable
 - iii) neutral
 - iv) somewhat acceptable

v) completely acceptable

- Please describe a situation where using the AI would be beneficial for assessing the quality.
- Please describe a situation where using the AI would be harmful for assessing the quality.

3) **Consider that TechForYou relies on RecruitTalent’s AI to assess an applicant’s quality and evaluate their chance of being hired. RecruitTalent identified an issue with its AI where it offers higher chances of being hired to brunettes over non-brunettes, even if they have a low potential. To address this, RecruitTalent modifies the AI to mitigate the issue.**

- Please describe how ‘the AI modification’ could be beneficial for everyone.

Modifying the AI has some side effects, which are described as different scenarios in parts (a), (b), (c) and (d). Please indicate your preference for the following scenarios:

a) **A side effect of modifying the AI is that it incorrectly predicts lower chances of being hired for high potential applicants. It is impossible to completely stop favoring brunettes and still provide correct chance of being hired for high potential applicants. In this scenario, if you were an applicant, which option would you suggest for RecruitTalent to choose?**

- i) The AI strongly favors brunettes; otherwise, it provides the correct chance of being hired.
- ii) The AI moderately favors brunettes, and it provides slightly incorrect chance of being hired.
- iii) The AI slightly favors brunettes, and it provides moderately incorrect chance of being hired.
- iv) The AI does not favor brunettes, and it provides highly incorrect chance of being hired

- Give an example of potential issues if RecruitTalent chooses a different approach than your suggestion.

b) **A side effect of modifying the AI is that TechForYou can learn whether an applicant has a criminal background by identifying if they were part of RecruitTalent’s data used to create the AI. It is impossible to completely stop favoring brunettes and still prevent TechForYou from identifying an applicant has a criminal background. In this scenario, if you were an applicant, which option would you suggest for RecruitTalent to choose?**

- i) The AI strongly favors brunettes, and it has no chance to reveal whether the applicant has a criminal background.
 - ii) The AI moderately favors brunettes, and it has a slight chance to reveal whether the applicant has a criminal background.
 - iii) The AI slightly favors brunettes, and it has a moderate chance to reveal whether the applicant has a criminal background.
 - iv) The AI does not favor brunettes, and it has a high chance to reveal whether the applicant has a criminal background.
 - Give an example of potential issues if RecruitTalent chooses a different approach than your suggestion.
- c) **A side effect of modifying the AI is that TechForYou can now determine the number of women in RecruitTalent’s data used to create the AI. It is impossible to completely stop favoring brunettes and still protect the information about the number of women. In this scenario, if you were an applicant, which option would you suggest for RecruitTalent to choose?**
- i) The AI strongly favors brunettes, and it has no chance to reveal the number of women in the data.
 - ii) The AI moderately favors brunettes, and it has a slight chance to reveal the number of women in the data.
 - iii) The AI slightly favors brunettes, and it has a moderate chance to reveal the number of women in the data.
 - iv) The AI does not favor brunettes, and it has a high chance to reveal the number of women in the data.
 - Give an example of potential issues if RecruitTalent chooses a different approach than your suggestion.
- d) **A side effect of modifying the AI is that TechForYou’s employees could exploit the AI to disadvantage blue-eyed applicants by giving them a lower chances of being hired. It is impossible to completely stop favoring brunettes and protect the AI from manipulation. In this scenario, if you were an applicant, which option would you suggest for RecruitTalent to choose?**
- i) The AI strongly favors brunettes, and it is highly difficult to manipulate.
 - ii) The AI moderately favors brunettes, and it is moderately difficult to manipulate.
 - iii) The AI slightly favors brunettes, and it is slightly difficult to manipulate.
 - iv) The AI does not favor brunettes, and it is not difficult to manipulate.
 - Give an example of potential issues if RecruitTalent chooses a different approach than your suggestion.

2 Demographic Information

- 1) What is your gender?
 - Man | Woman | Non-Binary | Prefer not to answer | Self-describe [text input]
- 2) Do you identify as being part of any minority groups?
 - Yes | No | Prefer not to answer
- 3) What age group do you belong to?
 - 18-25 | 26-35 | 36-45 | 46-55 | 56-65 | Prefer not to answer
- 4) What is your highest level of education?
 - Less than a high school degree | High school degree or equivalent [Non-university education beyond high-school (technical college, community college, vocational education) | Some college, no degree | Bachelor's or Associate's degree | Master's degree | Doctoral degree | Prefer not to answer
- 5) Are you a practitioner (researcher, working professional) in Machine Learning?
 - Yes | No | Prefer not to answer
- 6) Please provide your Prolific ID, this is important to get the compensation.